

TEACHERS' PRACTICES AND STUDENTS' ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT: BASIS FOR SCHOOL DEVELOPMENT PROGRAM

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ABSTRACT

Teachers' practices play a pivotal role in shaping the academic achievement of students, transforming classrooms into dynamic spaces where engagement and support foster academic excellence. The "Engagement-Driven Academic Success Theory" emphasizes the role of interactive teachers' practices in enhancing students' academic achievement. This study includes analyzing the characteristics of respondents and evaluating teachers' practices in various aspects such as classroom participation, extracurricular activities, personalized attention, professional development, parental communication, lesson preparation, collaboration with colleagues, and innovative teaching methods. Additionally, the study seeks to assess students' academic achievement in English, Science, Mathematics, Filipino, and Araling Panlipunan, identify the significant effects of teachers' practices on academic achievement, determine the relationship between teachers' practices and respondents' characteristics, and propose a school development program. The research surveyed four hundred six (406) teachers and eight hundred twelve (812) learners from the Valencia City Division who participated in the study. Data from the respondents was gathered using research-made questionnaires. The study employed a complete enumeration method to include the total population in the research. Data analysis involved descriptive statistics, mean, standard deviation, Pearson Moment Correlation, and a one-way ANOVA to draw meaningful conclusions about the relationship between teacher practices and academic achievement. Findings showed that certain aspects of teacher practices, such as lesson preparation and parental communication, had significant positive correlations with academic achievement in specific subjects. The study recommends targeted strategies to promote teacher engagement and student academic achievement, including professional development programs, support for extracurricular activities, and collaboration among educators.

Keywords: *Teachers' Practices, Students' Achievement*

INTRODUCTION

Teachers provide students with a wide range of support, including academic instruction, emotional assistance, appraisal, and instrumental guidance. They also create a positive learning environment that fosters student growth and success. They are at the forefront of education, where students have high expectations for the learning that will mold them into independent and competitive individuals. Indeed, teachers are widely recognized as key figures who influence students' psychological well-being, behavior, and academic success.

As, Inayat and Alit (2020) emphasized the importance of educational institutions providing professional development training to teachers for effective content delivery and lesson preparation. Despite ongoing training, students may still lack motivation in the classroom, leading to low participation and performance. Effective delivery of the school curriculum by teachers can foster activities, collaboration, and innovative teaching methods, positively impacting students' academic performance. Facilitating meaningful learning experiences can inspire students to showcase their talents, enhance motivation, and channel their interest productively towards academics.

The Republic Act (RA) No. 4670, also known as the Magna Carta for Public School Teachers, focuses on safeguarding the physical and mental health of teachers while regulating their work hours for lesson preparation and teaching responsibilities. Additionally, teachers play a crucial role in the Department of Education (DepEd), ensuring the delivery of the curriculum and services and promoting a holistic approach to classroom leadership. Teachers are pivotal in creating a student-centered learning environment and safeguarding the well-being of learners. It is vital for DepEd to alleviate teachers' non-work-related burdens to enhance the curriculum and establish a more supportive learning atmosphere.

Similarly, for students to succeed in learning a foreign language, teachers must be actively involved and confident in their abilities (Bao et al., 2021, 2022). However, teacher engagement showed a negative relationship with burnout. While students play a primary role in their learning and success, teachers and parents also significantly impact school advancement.

Teachers have expressed concerns regarding professional development, citing limited opportunities for external seminars, delays in scheduled activities, and challenges in implementing faculty development (Padillo, 2021). Inadequate lesson planning, inappropriate strategies, and classroom management issues can hinder teachers from meeting their teaching objectives, impacting students' learning goals (Ali, 2021). Some educators face difficulties in communicating with parents, providing personalized attention, and dedicating ample time for lesson planning. Factors affecting innovative teaching methods, such as personal dedication, teaching philosophies, commitment, and

expertise, pose challenges that prompt teachers to collaborate with peers (Hashim et al., 2019).

Addressing these challenges is crucial to fostering innovation and creativity among teachers, ensuring effective mechanisms to achieve educational goals. Even with attempts to tackle these obstacles, there is a need for further action to guarantee that teachers and students truly reap the rewards of proper lesson preparation and classroom management. As Khan (2020) highlighted, this could mean introducing more inclusive and thorough educational initiatives to empower teachers to manage the intricate aspects of lesson planning and classroom management effectively.

The study aims to understand the relationship between teacher practices and academic achievement, considering factors such as position, teaching experience, highest educational attainment, and subject taught. By examining how these variables interact with teacher involvement, a more comprehensive understanding can be achieved.

Moreover, it would be beneficial to examine any potential differences in the effectiveness of teacher practices across different subject areas (English, Math, Science, Filipino, and Araling Panlipunan). Variations in teaching methodologies, content complexity, and student interest levels may lead to differential impacts on academic achievement within each subject domain.

Furthermore, considering the unique cultural and contextual factors within the Valencia City Division, exploring any specific challenges or opportunities related to teacher practices and student achievement could provide valuable insights for enhancing educational practices in the division.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the student's academic achievement in the Division of Valencia City during the School Year 2023–2024. The result of the study would be the basis for a school development program. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the characteristics of the respondents in terms of position, teaching experience, highest educational attainment, and subject taught?
2. How do the respondents assess their practices- with regard to classroom participation, extracurricular activities, personalized attention, professional development, parental communication, lesson preparation, collaboration with colleagues, and innovative teaching methods?
3. What is the level of learners' academic achievement in English, Science, Mathematics, Filipino, and Araling Panlipunan during the 3rd and 4th Quarters?
4. Is there a significant effect of teacher practices on learners' academic achievement?
5. Is there a significant relationship between teachers' practices and each of their characteristics?
6. Based on the study's findings, what school development program can be designed?

METHODOLOGY

This section presented the techniques and protocols used in the research investigation. It provided in-depth descriptions of the research design, setting, respondents, research instrument, instrument validation, data gathering procedure, statistical treatment of the data, and ethical considerations of the study.

Research Design

This research study was underpinned by a descriptive method, a crucial choice that allowed to determine the level of teachers' involvement and academic achievement of public junior high school students. This method, by its very nature, enabled to establish the level of teacher practices based on various factors and how these variables influence the academic achievement of the learners.

Additionally, descriptive research design was widely employed across diverse fields. Its primary objective was to systematically observe and document all variables and conditions influencing the phenomenon (Singh, 2023). This method formulated its hypothesis as data were collected. The descriptive research design disallowed interventions or manipulation of the variables. The first goal was to seek the level of teacher involvement in academic achievement among all study respondents. It was then very appropriate to use the implied research design.

Study Setting

A research study was meticulously carried out in the Department of Education, Division of Valencia City, focusing on medium, large, and mega schools within the division. The selection of participating schools was carefully done to ensure diverse representation and respondent cooperation. Valencia City, officially known as the City of Valencia, is a 2nd-class component city in Bukidnon, Philippines, with a population of 216,546 as per the 2020 census. It became a city under Republic Act No. 8985 in January 2001, standing as the most populous inland city in Mindanao and a key hub for trade and commerce in Bukidnon. The study's location in the highly populated Valencia City Division provided valuable insights. The researchers strategically sampled schools of various sizes to gather comprehensive data, with a focus on respondents' voluntary participation to ensure data accuracy. The study's setting was chosen meticulously to align with the research criteria, ensuring the collection of pertinent and reliable information.

Research Respondents

The study was conducted in the Valencia City division. The participating teachers were from a mix of medium, large, and mega secondary schools within this division. The 406 teachers represented a cross-section of the teaching staff in the area. The 812 student participants were from the junior high school department, meaning they were in grades 7–10, in the same Valencia City division. The study focused on the academic

performance of these students across five core subject areas: English, science, mathematics, Filipino, and Araling Panlipunan.

The table below shows the distribution of respondents by school.

Distribution of Respondents

Name/Category of School	Total # of Respondents
A. Medium School	
A.1. Catumbalon National High School	29
A.2. Guinoyoran National High School	17
A.3. Lilingayon National High School	25
A.4. Conception National High School	18
B. Large School	
B.1. Lurugan National High School	45
B.2. Tongan-Tongan National High School	45
C. Mega School	
C.1. Valencia National High School	227
Total	406

Sampling Technique

The researcher employed a complete enumeration method to determine the total population for this study. All 406 Valencia City Division secondary school teachers were included as respondents. This approach was opted for the small sample size, which allowed for precise statistical analysis considering the entire test statistic distribution. Additionally, the 812 student participants from the junior high school department were also part of the complete enumeration, with data collected on their academic performance across the five core subject areas. The data analysis examined all possible elements in the finite teacher and student information set, providing a representative snapshot of the Valencia City education system. Descriptive statistics analysed the data, the Pearson correlation coefficient, and a one-way ANOVA. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize and characterize the key variables, such as teacher demographic profile and student academic performance. The study computed the Pearson correlation coefficient to analyse the links between variables, including teacher qualifications, teaching experience, and student achievement. The study conducted a one-way ANOVA to find out if there were any statistically significant differences in student achievement based on various teaching practices. This comprehensive analytical approach allowed the researchers to thoroughly understand the factors influencing academic performance within the Valencia City secondary schools.

Research Instruments

The data collection instrument for this study was a survey questionnaire designed to gather valuable insights into teachers' practices and their effect on student's academic achievement. The researcher developed and validated the research instrument.

The first part included questions about the teachers' respondents' profiles, such as position, teaching experience, highest educational attainment, and subject taught. The second part of the survey questionnaire focused on various aspects of teachers' practices in classroom participation, extracurricular activities, personalized attention, professional development, parental communication, lesson preparation, collaboration with colleagues, and innovative teaching methods. The last part of the questionnaire assessed the learner's academic achievement in English, Science, Mathematics, Filipino, and Araling Panlipunan.

The finalized survey questionnaire was then administered to a representative sample of participants from medium, large, and mega schools within the Division of Valencia City. Participation in the study was voluntary, and the researchers considered the respondents' willingness to cooperate during the data collection process.

Validity and Reliability of Instrument

The study utilized a researcher-made survey questionnaire as the data collection instrument, which underwent rigorous validation to ensure reliability and validity. Content validity was confirmed through consultation with three education experts, who unanimously agreed that the instrument comprehensively addressed key constructs related to teachers' practices and learners' academic achievement. The survey questionnaire was endorsed for its relevance, format adherence, and suitability in academic and research contexts.

To establish reliability, internal consistency using Cronbach's alpha and test-retest reliability were employed. The survey questionnaire demonstrated a very high level of internal consistency with an overall Cronbach's alpha value of 0.957. Factor analysis confirmed the instrument's construct validity, ensuring effective measurement of intended factors and variables.

Pilot testing was crucial in refining the survey instrument based on participant feedback, enhancing clarity and comprehensibility. The finalized survey instrument was then administered to participants from various school categories within the Division of Valencia City, with voluntary participation ensuring cooperation during data collection. This validated instrument provided reliable data for examining the relationship between teachers' practices and students' academic achievement, laying the foundation for a school development program.

Categorization of Variables and System of Scoring

The following categories were created to facilitate data analysis and interpretation.

Part 1. Respondent's Characteristics

Position

Master Teacher III

Master Teacher II

Master Teacher I

Teacher III

Teacher II

Teacher I

Teaching Experience

30 years and above

25-29 years

20-24 years

15-19 years

10-14 years

5-9 years

4 years and below

Highest Educational Attainment

Doctorate Degree

Master's Degree with PhD Units

Master's Degree

Bachelor's Degree with MA Units

Bachelor's Degree

Subject Taught

English

Science

Mathematics

Filipino

Araling Panlipunan

Part 2. Teacher Involvement

Scale	Range	Description	Interpretation
4	3.21 – 4.00	Always	Very High
3	2.61 – 3.20	Most of the Time	High
2	1.81 – 2.60	Sometimes	Low
1	1.00 – 1.80	Never	Very Low

PART 3. Academic Achievement

Grade Average	Description
90 and above	Outstanding
85 to 89	Very Satisfactory
80 to 84	Satisfactory
75 to 79	Fairly Satisfactory
74 and below	Does Not Meet Expectations

Data Gathering Procedure

Prior to commencing the data gathering activity, the researcher obtained approvals from the Dean of Graduate Studies at PHINMA Cagayan de Oro College and the DepEd Valencia City Division Superintendent. Approval from the seven participating school heads was secured after submitting a research consent letter, allowing for the initiation of data collection procedures.

The two-week data collection activity began following approvals from relevant authorities and school heads, resulting in a 100% recovery rate from 406 teacher respondents. Before distributing the research questionnaire, a brief orientation was conducted to stress the importance of honest responses for unbiased and valid results.

The researcher employed Google Suite to create a data collection form, utilizing technology to reach teacher respondents in remote areas safely and efficiently. The Google Forms link was shared via email and messaging platforms, accompanied by clear instructions and deadlines. Follow-up reminders were sent to enhance response rates. Data collected through the online form was automatically organized and securely stored in a database, facilitating efficient and accurate data analysis.

Statistical Treatment of Data

This study used descriptive statistics to analyse and interpret the data, providing a clear overview of the study results and discussions. Descriptive statistics help outline the key characteristics of the data, offering basic descriptions of the sample and measurements, which are essential for most quantitative data analyses and are complemented by straightforward graphical representations for analysis.

For Problem 1, the respondents' characteristics in terms of position, teaching experience, highest educational attainment, subject taught, frequency, and percentage were used. For Problem 2, on the level of teachers' practices, the mean and standard deviation were employed and presented in tables. However, in Problem 3, the assessment of academic achievement, frequency, and percentage were used. In Problem 4, regression analysis determined the significant effect of teachers' practices and academic achievements. This further analysed whether the set null hypothesis is acceptable or not. However, in Problem 5, to determine the significant relationship between academic achievement and the respondents' characteristics, Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) was utilized. This demonstrated whether the two variables were correlated or related.

Ethical Considerations

The research study prioritized ethical considerations to protect the rights of human participants and uphold research integrity. Ethics review and approval were obtained, with voluntary participation for teacher respondents and parental consent for student participants. Confidentiality measures were strictly implemented to safeguard potentially identifiable data, ensuring data privacy and trust.

The study's goals encompassed understanding real-life phenomena, effective treatments, and academic behaviour. Written, informed consent was obtained to protect participants' rights, with a focus on maintaining confidentiality in potential publication content. Ethical considerations extended to the dissemination of research findings, emphasizing the importance of accuracy, benefit, and respect for participant confidentiality in contributing to academic knowledge advancement.

RESULTS

This section outlines the study's key components, including results, interpretation, and analysis, aiming to drive positive changes in teachers' practices and student success through the portrayal, explanation, and application of research results.

Problem 1. What are the respondents' characteristics regarding position, teaching experience, highest educational attainment, and subject taught?

Table 1. Respondents Characteristics

Indicator	Frequency	Percentage
Teaching Position		
Teacher 1	243	59.85
Teacher 2	60	14.78
Teacher 3	72	17.73
Master Teacher 1	31	7.63
Master Teacher 2	0	0.00
Master Teacher 3	0	0.00
Total	406	100.00
Teaching Experience		
	Frequency	Percentage
21 and above	57	14.04
16-20 years	43	10.59
11-15 years	65	16.01
6-10 years	160	39.41
0-5 years	81	19.95
Total	406	100.00
Highest Educational Attainment		
	Frequency	Percentage
Doctorate Degree	0	0.00
Master's degree w/PhD	51	12.56
Master's Degree	102	25.12
Bachelor's Degree w/MA	173	42.61
Bachelor's Degree	80	19.70
Total	406	100.00
Subject Taught		
	Frequency	Percentage
English	66	16.26
Science	74	18.23
Math	66	16.26
Filipino	74	18.23
Araling Panlipunan	77	18.97
Other Subjects	49	12.07
Total	406	100.00

The distribution of respondents' characteristics revealed a significant presence of teachers in the Teacher 1 position, comprising 59.85% of the respondents. This high frequency may be attributed to turnover rates, limited career progression options, or a disparity between the supply and demand of experienced teachers. To address these challenges, the study suggests fostering a supportive work environment, structured career pathways, and comprehensive professional development opportunities to enhance teacher retention and success (Hattie, 2019).

On the other hand, the Master Teacher 1 position had the lowest frequency, with only 7.64% of respondents occupying this role. Barriers such as limited training access, lack of mentorship, and insufficient incentives for higher qualifications may contribute to the scarcity of teachers in advanced positions. The study recommends implementing professional development initiatives, mentorship programs, clear career paths,

recognition incentives, and supportive leadership to address this gap (Vagi et al., 2019). The absence of Master Teacher 2 and Master Teacher 3 positions signifies a significant void in top-tier professional recognition and expertise, suggesting potential barriers hindering teachers from advancing to these higher levels.

The research underscores the significance of investing in the growth of early-career educators, establishing clear career pathways, and offering advanced teaching roles to attract and retain high-performing teachers. By tackling these issues, educational institutions can cultivate a more experienced, engaged, and effective teaching workforce, ultimately leading to enhanced student outcomes.

The distribution of respondents based on teaching experience indicated that 39.41% were in the 6–10-year category, a crucial period for educators to refine their instructional practices and become expert teachers. Research by Kraft and Falken underscores the significance of comprehensive, sustained, and content-focused professional development programs to enhance teacher practices and student outcomes. These programs should be multifaceted, sustained, and tailored to teachers' needs to improve student achievements and cultivate a proficient teaching workforce.

However, 10.59% of respondents fell into the 16–20-year experience range, suggesting potential mid-career attrition due to burnout, lack of support, and work-life balance issues. Implementing personalized professional development, mentorship initiatives, and work-life balance programs is essential to retain experienced educators and contribute to long-term student success and the educational community. The study by Vagi, Pivovarova, and Barnard (2019) emphasizes the importance of targeted support and retention strategies, beyond the initial induction phase, to mitigate teacher attrition and enhance the overall teaching workforce quality.

The distribution of respondents based on their highest educational attainment revealed that 42.61% held a bachelor's degree with a master's degree, showcasing a workforce that values continuing education and professional development. Teachers with advanced degrees often possess enhanced content knowledge and pedagogical skills, leading to improved student outcomes and effective classroom management. Higher levels of educational attainment among teachers have been linked to better student performance and more effective teaching practices (Darling-Hammond et al., 2020).

Ghanizadeh and Rostami's study (2021) highlighted that teachers with a master's degree exhibit higher self-efficacy and confidence in various aspects of teaching, contributing to improved student achievement and job satisfaction. However, the low representation of teachers with a master's degree and a PhD suggests potential barriers to pursuing doctoral-level education. Strategies to incentivize and support advanced degrees are crucial to attract and retain highly educated teachers and enhance the quality of the teaching workforce.

The distribution of respondents based on the subject taught highlighted a notable presence of teachers in Araling Panlipunan, potentially influenced by curricular

requirements and student interest. In contrast, subjects like Music, Arts, Physical Education, Health Education (MAPEH), Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao (ESP), and Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) had lower frequencies, indicating a focus on core academic subjects over elective or specialized areas. Addressing this imbalance through interdisciplinary integration and targeted professional development initiatives could bolster the teaching workforce in these subjects and promote a more well-rounded curriculum for holistic student development.

Cohen and Hill's study (2020) stresses the importance of a balanced curriculum in nurturing multiple intelligences, enhancing student engagement, and fostering equity and inclusion. Integrating non-core subjects like MAPEH, ESP, and TLE can enrich the learning experience, establish interdisciplinary connections, and cater to diverse student interests and talents. By rectifying disparities in subject representation, educational institutions can establish a more inclusive learning environment that empowers all students to realize their full potential.

Problem 2. How do the respondents assess their practices in classroom participation, extracurricular activities, personalized attention, professional development, parental communication, lesson preparation, collaboration with colleagues, and innovative teaching methods?

Table 2.1. Distribution of Respondents' Assessment of their Practices in Classroom Participation

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
As a teacher...			
I lead the discussions and activities to motivate students to participate throughout the period.	3.70	0.46	Always
I promote student participation to enrich both creativity and mind-fullness.	3.72	0.45	Always
I ensure that classroom participation is a positive experience for every student.	3.75	0.44	Always
I encourage students to share their thoughts and opinions in class to enhance self-confidence.	3.79	0.41	Always
I employ interactive teaching methods like discussions, debates, or Q&A sessions for student engagement.	3.50	0.58	Always
I use approaches to actively involve students in hands-on activities or group work during lessons.	3.58	0.53	Always
I empower students to ask questions and engage in meaningful dialogue.	3.64	0.53	Always
I facilitate the discussions and activities for a better understanding of the concepts.	3.70	0.46	Always
I engage my students in interactive discussions and develop better outcomes.	3.65	0.49	Always
I provide feedback and foster a collaborative learning	3.54	0.57	Always

environment.

Overall	3.66	0.49	Always
<i>Legend :</i>	3.21-4.00 <i>Always/Very High</i>	2.61-3.20 <i>Most of the Time/High</i>	
	1.81-2.60 <i>Sometimes/Low</i>	1.00-1.80 <i>Never/ Very Low</i>	

Table 2.1 analyzes teachers' classroom participation practices, showing a mean of 3.66 (SD = 0.49), indicating consistent engagement. Factors like training, resource access, and institutional support contribute to this engagement. Zhong and Li (2020) highlight the positive impact of teacher engagement on student achievement, especially in online learning environments. Strengthening interactive teaching approaches can enhance students' learning outcomes.

Encouraging students to share thoughts and opinions promotes self-confidence, inclusivity, and motivation in the classroom. Student self-efficacy predicts academic success, making student expression crucial for their engagement and motivation. Interactive methods like discussions, debates, and Q&A sessions, with a mean score of 3.50 (SD = 0.58), demonstrate a commitment to engaging students. However, there is room for improvement and innovation in their implementation.

Interactive methods like discussions and debates enhance understanding, critical thinking, and communication skills. Cochrane et al. (2019) emphasize that active participation fosters critical thinking, engagement, and skill development. These methods not only enhance academic performance but also prepare students for future success by developing essential skills like communication and teamwork.

Table 2.2. Distribution of Respondents Assessment of their Practices in Engagement in Extracurricular Activities

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
As a teacher...			
I take an active role in planning and managing extracurricular activities.	3.11	0.72	Most of the Time
I initiate and organize extracurricular activities to enhance the talents of my students.	3.02	0.74	Most of the Time
I organize or lead some extracurricular activities relevant to the appropriate grade-level competencies.	2.98	0.77	Most of the Time
I participate in extracurricular activities outside of the scheduled school day.	2.94	0.83	Most of the Time
I encourage and assist students who want to participate in extracurricular activities.	3.32	0.70	Always
I eagerly participate in extracurricular activities to share my knowledge and skills.	3.13	1.40	Most of the Time
I attend and support students during extracurricular events, such as sports competitions or performances.	3.26	0.69	Always
I render extra hours to help motivate students to pursue extracurricular activities.	3.04	0.73	Most of the Time
I am involved in supervising and coordinating school clubs or societies.	2.96	0.81	Most of the Time
I allow project collaboration as part of extracurricular initiatives.	3.12	0.74	Most of the Time

Overall	3.09	0.81	Most of the Time
<i>Legend :</i>	3.21-4.00 Always/Very High	2.61-3.20 Most of the Time/High	
	1.81-2.60 Sometimes/Low	1.00-1.80 Never/ Very Low	

The analysis of teacher practices in engagement in extracurricular activities reveals a high commitment level, with an overall mean of 3.09 (SD = 0.81). While teachers show dedication to holistic student development, there are disparities in participation levels across schools. Encouraging uniform practices through policies and support systems can maximize the benefits of extracurricular activities, promoting equity and inclusion.

One teacher, focusing on encouraging student participation, achieved a high mean score of 3.32 (SD = 0.70), reflecting a very high commitment level. Consistent support for students in extracurricular activities fosters holistic education, empowering students to explore interests and develop life skills. Teacher encouragement plays a vital role in promoting student success and participation in these activities, as highlighted by Rodriguez and Martinez (2020).

Conversely, teacher participation in extracurricular activities outside the scheduled school day received a lower mean of 2.94 (SD = 0.83), indicating room for improvement in consistency. The variability in engagement suggests factors like support, resources, and motivation influence educators' involvement. Addressing these challenges can strengthen a holistic approach to education, ensuring equal emphasis on academic and non-academic aspects.

Table 2.3. Distribution of Respondents' Assessment of their Practices in Personalized Attention

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
As a teacher...			
I offer personalized support to students who encounter academic challenges.	3.34	0.61	Always
I adjust my teaching methods to meet each student's individual needs and learning interests.	3.52	0.55	Always
I regularly integrate interests and preferences into the curriculum to ensure personalized learning experiences.	3.45	0.57	Always
I identify and address individual learning difficulties by offering additional support and resources to students.	3.33	0.61	Always
I schedule individual conferences or meetings with students to discuss their goals and progress.	3.23	0.68	Always
I tailor my teaching methods to meet the specific learning needs of each student.	3.34	0.61	Always
I consistently provide personalized feedback to individual students regarding their academic progress.	3.33	0.61	Always
I give each student individualized feedback to ensure their academic needs are met.	3.34	0.60	Always
I consistently provide individualized feedback to students on their assignments and assessments.	3.21	0.64	Always
I employ teaching strategies that cater to the diverse learning needs of each student for an inclusive learning environment.	3.38	0.61	Always

Overall	3.35	0.61	Always
Legend :	3.21-4.00 Always/Very High	2.61-3.20 Most of the Time/High	
	1.81-2.60 Sometimes/Low	1.00-1.80 Never/ Very Low	

The analysis of personalized attention practices among teachers reveals a high level of commitment, with an overall mean score of 3.35 (SD = 0.61), described as very high. Teachers consistently provide individualized support, adapting their teaching methods to meet the unique needs of each student. This personalized approach is crucial for addressing diverse learning needs and fostering student engagement and academic success.

One teacher, focusing on adjusting teaching methods to meet individual student needs, achieved a high mean score of 3.52 (SD = 0.55), indicating a strong emphasis on personalized teaching. Adapting teaching strategies to align with students' needs and interests creates an inclusive and effective learning environment, supporting equitable learning opportunities.

In contrast, providing individualized feedback to students on assignments and assessments received a slightly lower mean score of 3.21 (SD = 0.64), suggesting challenges in consistent implementation. Time constraints and workload issues can hinder educators from delivering personalized feedback effectively, highlighting the need for additional support and strategies to maintain this practice consistently.

The research by Cohen and Hill (2020), Darling-Hammond et al. (2020), Hattie (2019), Ingersoll and Strong (2019), and Shute (2019) emphasizes the importance of personalized teaching strategies, mentoring programs, and individualized feedback in supporting student learning, engagement, and academic performance. These studies underscore the transformative impact of personalized approaches on student growth and success, highlighting the significance of ongoing professional development and institutional support in enhancing teaching practices.

Table 2.4. Distribution of Respondents' Assessment of their Practices in Professional Development

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
<i>As a teacher...</i>			
I improve my teaching abilities by taking part in professional development training.	3.43	0.65	Always
I participate in ongoing training sessions the school or district offers to stay informed about educational trends.	3.39	0.64	Always
I proactively seek and engage in various professional development opportunities to refine my skills and expertise.	3.36	0.64	Always
I attend workshops, conferences, or seminars to enhance my teaching skills and knowledge.	3.32	0.65	Always
I pursue advanced degrees or additional certifications to further develop my expertise in the subject matter.	3.20	0.74	Most of the Time
I remain abreast of the latest educational approaches and advancements for continuous improvement in my practice.	3.29	0.62	Always

I remain abreast of the latest educational approaches and advancements for continuous improvement in my practice.	3.45	0.59	Always
I collaborate with colleagues to share best practices and innovative teaching strategies as part of my personal and professional development.	3.36	0.65	Always
I engage in reflective practice and establish personal and professional development goals for continuous improvement.	3.33	0.59	Always
I apply insights gained from professional development in my daily teaching practices.	3.39	0.60	Always
Overall	3.35	0.64	Always
<i>Legend :</i>	3.21-4.00 Always/Very High	2.61-3.20 Most of the Time/High	
	1.81-2.60 Sometimes/Low	1.00-1.80 Never/ Very Low	

The analysis of teachers' practices in professional development indicates a high level of commitment, with an overall mean score of 3.35 (SD = 0.64), categorized as Very High. Teachers show consistent engagement in professional development activities, highlighting a strong dedication to continuous improvement and growth in their teaching practices. Ongoing participation in professional development is crucial for enhancing teaching skills, keeping abreast of educational trends, and enhancing student outcomes.

Padillo (2021) emphasizes the significant impact of professional development on improving teaching practices and student learning outcomes. These programs equip teachers with essential skills and strategies to deliver effective and personalized instruction, ultimately enhancing student engagement and academic success. Research by Adeniran, Ishaku, and Akanni (2020) also underscores the importance of continuous professional development in maintaining teacher engagement and addressing learning disparities.

Sanchez (2022) and Ansong (2024) highlight the necessity of well-designed professional development programs tailored to meet the specific needs of teachers and students. These initiatives provide practical strategies that can be directly implemented in the classroom, significantly influencing teaching practices, confidence, and job satisfaction. Continuous learning through professional development is vital for teachers to navigate challenges and ensure a high-quality education for students.

One indicator, focusing on staying informed about the latest educational approaches, received the highest mean score of 3.45 (SD = 0.59), reflecting a strong commitment to continuous learning and adaptation. Teachers who remain updated on educational advancements can implement innovative teaching strategies, enhancing student engagement, motivation, and academic achievement.

On the other hand, the indicator related to pursuing advanced degrees or additional certifications received a lower mean score of 3.20 (SD = 0.74), indicating challenges in consistent engagement with further education. Darling-Hammond et al. (2019) emphasize the importance of advanced education and specialized training in deepening subject matter expertise, adapting teaching strategies, and meeting diverse learning needs. Educators with higher levels of education are more likely to integrate innovative teaching techniques and benefit from ongoing learning opportunities.

Table 2.5. Distribution of Respondents' Assessment of their Practices in Parental Communication

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
As a teacher...			
I regularly communicate with parents or guardians regarding their child's academic progress.	3.43	0.60	Always
I promote parents' involvement in supporting their child's education and in a collaborative home-school partnership.	3.51	0.57	Always
I promptly respond to messages from parents seeking information or updates about their child's education to ensure open lines of communication.	3.56	0.55	Always
I organize quarterly parent-teacher conferences, or as needed, to discuss students' overall development and performance.	3.54	0.56	Always
I provide parents with opportunities for teaching methods and classroom activities to enhance transparency.	3.33	0.67	Always
I communicate with parents about the child's behavioral issues or concerns that need to be addressed.	3.52	0.61	Always
I share information about upcoming school events, projects, or assignments with parents.	3.50	0.60	Always
I actively seek parental input and involvement in the child's educational journey for shared decision-making.	3.41	0.60	Always
I regularly provide constructive feedback to parents on ways they can support their child's learning at home to promote effective home-school partnerships.	3.39	0.64	Always
I collaborate with parents to address academic challenges and improve coping mechanisms.	3.39	0.60	Always
Overall	3.46	0.60	Always
<i>Legend :</i>			
	3.21-4.00	Always/Very High	2.61-3.20
	1.81-2.60	Sometimes/Low	1.00-1.80
			Never/ Very Low

The analysis of teachers' practices in parental communication reveals a high level of commitment, with an overall mean score of 3.46 (SD = 0.60), described as Very High. Teachers consistently engage in effective communication with parents, emphasizing the importance of maintaining open and meaningful dialogue to enhance student success and the educational experience.

Research by Tutt (2021) and Hawthorne (2022) highlights the significance of effective parental communication in education, addressing common challenges and fostering strong home-school partnerships. Effective communication leads to improved student outcomes, enhanced teacher provision, and increased parent engagement in their child's education.

One indicator, focusing on promptly responding to parent messages seeking information or updates about their child's education, received the highest mean score of 3.56 (SD = 0.55), demonstrating a strong commitment to maintaining open lines of communication. This practice fosters trust, collaboration, and positive relationships between parents and teachers, contributing to student well-being and academic success.

In contrast, the indicator of providing parents with opportunities to learn about teaching methods and classroom activities received a lower mean score of 3.33 (SD = 0.67). While educators value transparency and parent involvement, there may be variability in how consistently these opportunities are provided, indicating a need for more structured approaches to enhance parent engagement.

Table 2.6. Distribution of Respondents' Assessment of their Practices in Time Spent on Lesson Preparation

Indicators	Men	SD	Description
As a teacher....			
I dedicate time to plan and prepare for daily lessons thoroughly.	3.41	0.56	Always
I engage in strategic long-term curriculum planning to ensure comprehensive coverage of topics throughout the academic year.	3.29	0.62	Always
I invest extra time beyond regular school hours to prepare materials and resources for classroom instruction.	3.31	0.60	Always
I update and adapt lesson plans to address the evolving needs of the students.	3.44	0.56	Always
I use a variety of assessments (e.g., essays, quizzes, projects) that align with learning objectives and accurately measure student understanding of the course material.	3.54	0.54	Always
I collaborate with colleagues to share lesson plans and resources, reducing individual preparation time.	3.34	0.63	Always
I participate in professional development activities focused on improving lesson planning and preparation skills.	3.34	0.63	Always
I allocate time for reflection on the teaching practices and adjust to improve student learning.	3.36	0.58	Always
I involve students in planning to solicit their input and feedback on learning activities to enhance relevance and engagement.	3.25	0.65	Always
I invest additional time in planning and organizing initiatives relevant to the lesson.	3.27	0.63	Always
Overall	3.35	0.60	Always
<i>Legend : 3.21-4.00 Always/Very High 2.61-3.20 Most of the Time/High 1.81-2.60 Sometimes/Low 1.00-1.80 Never/ Very Low</i>			

The analysis of teachers' professional development practices indicates a high level of commitment, with an overall mean score of 3.35 (SD = 0.64), signifying a Very High dedication to continuous improvement. Teachers exhibit consistent engagement in professional development activities, emphasizing the importance of ongoing learning to enhance teaching skills and student outcomes. Padillo (2021) highlights the significant impact of professional development on teaching practices and student learning, equipping educators with essential skills for effective instruction.

Research by Adeniran, Ishaku, and Akanni (2020) reinforces the necessity of continuous professional development to maintain teacher engagement and address learning disparities. Sanchez (2022) and Ansong (2024) stress the need for well-tailored professional development programs to meet the specific needs of teachers and students, enhancing teaching practices and job satisfaction. Staying informed about the latest educational approaches received the highest mean score, indicating a strong

commitment to continuous learning and adaptation, leading to innovative teaching strategies and improved student engagement.

Conversely, pursuing advanced degrees received a lower mean score, suggesting challenges in consistent engagement with further education. Darling-Hammond et al. (2019) underscore the importance of advanced education in deepening subject matter expertise and adapting teaching strategies. Educators with higher levels of education are more likely to integrate innovative teaching techniques and benefit from ongoing learning opportunities.

Table 2.7. Distribution of Respondents Assessment of their Practices in Collaboration with Colleagues

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description	
As a teacher....				
I collaborate with colleagues on joint lesson planning or curriculum development.	3.33	0.65	Always	
I participate in professional learning communities or collaborative teacher teams.	3.36	0.60	Always	
I share teaching strategies and resources with my colleagues to foster a collaborative learning environment.	3.32	0.61	Always	
I engage in interdisciplinary collaboration with colleagues from other subject areas.	3.32	0.66	Always	
I collaborate with colleagues to share insights and develop effective interventions.	3.42	0.61	Always	
I actively engage in collaborative professional development opportunities with colleagues, focusing on implementing evidence-based practices to enhance student learning outcomes.	3.44	0.59	Always	
I involve colleagues in discussions about innovative teaching methods and educational trends.	3.37	0.63	Always	
I work collaboratively with colleagues to create a supportive and cohesive classroom environment.	3.37	0.62	Always	
I help my colleagues to organize and supervise extracurricular activities.	3.32	0.61	Always	
I seek input and feedback from colleagues on their teaching practices for mutual professional growth and improvement.	3.36	0.63	Always	
Overall	3.36	0.62	Always	
Legend :	3.21-4.00	Always/Very High	2.61-3.20	Most of the Time/High
	1.81-2.60	Sometimes/Low	1.00-1.80	Never/ Very Low

Table 8 provides a comprehensive analysis of teachers' collaboration practices, revealing a strong culture of collaboration that enhances teaching effectiveness, problem-solving support, and professional growth. This collaborative environment fosters shared best practices and mutual support, promoting a supportive teaching community. Studies by Ruano (2019), Sannen et al. (2021), Muckenthaler et al. (2020), Drossel et al. (2019), and De Jong et al. (2022) align with these findings, emphasizing the positive impact of effective collaboration on student achievement and the importance of dense networks for inclusive teaching practices.

The research underscores the significance of teacher collaboration in professional development and educational effectiveness, leading to continuous improvement and better student outcomes. The high level of engagement in collaborative activities reflects a well-established norm among teachers, enhancing the professional environment and fostering growth. The emphasis on evidence-based practices and shared learning opportunities highlights educators' commitment to lifelong learning and skill enhancement.

While sharing teaching strategies and resources received a slightly lower mean score, educators still value collaboration and recognize its importance in fostering a supportive learning environment. Collaborative efforts not only enhance pedagogical skills and teaching effectiveness but also promote innovation, creativity, and job satisfaction among teachers. By working together, educators can create a culture of continuous improvement and excellence in education, benefiting both teachers and students alike.

Table 2.8. Distribution of Respondents' Assessment of their Practices in Innovative Teaching Methods

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
As a teacher...			
I integrate technology into my lessons to enhance student engagement.	3.53	0.60	Always
I employ various creative teaching approaches in the classroom to meet the needs of students with different learning styles and preferences.	3.44	0.60	Always
I facilitate project-based learning and hands-on experiential approaches in my teaching for active learning.	3.38	0.61	Always
I tailor-fit lessons to accommodate diverse learning styles and preferences for equitable learning opportunities.	3.35	0.58	Always
I utilize flipped classroom techniques for pre-learning before in-class discussions.	3.32	1.43	Always
I integrate real-world applications to contextualize content and enhance its relevance for students.	3.48	0.57	Always
I incorporate collaborative learning activities as teaching methods to develop teamwork among students.	3.56	1.93	Always
I utilize gamification strategies to increase student engagement and motivation.	3.26	0.66	Always
I incorporate creative assessment methods to gauge student understanding.	3.30	0.62	Always
I adapt different teaching approaches to match each student's needs and interests.	3.42	0.55	Always
Overall	3.40	0.82	Always

Legend : 3.21-4.00 Always/Very High 2.61-3.20 Most of the Time/High
1.81-2.60 Sometimes/Low 1.00-1.80 Never/ Very Low

The distribution analysis of respondents' practices in innovative teaching methods reveals a high level of commitment, with an overall mean score of 3.40 (SD = 0.82), described as Very High. Teachers demonstrate a strong willingness to incorporate innovative teaching

strategies, emphasizing student-centred approaches and dynamic instructional methods to enhance learning outcomes.

Research by Karolčík and Marková (2023) highlights the importance of teachers' perceptions of innovative teaching methods in designing effective professional development programs and support systems. Overcoming implementation challenges and fostering widespread adoption of innovative practices can positively impact student motivation, learning outcomes, and engagement.

One indicator, focusing on incorporating collaborative learning activities to develop teamwork among students, obtained the highest mean score of 3.56 (SD = 1.93), demonstrating educators' high value for collaborative learning. These activities promote social interaction, critical thinking, and essential interpersonal skills, contributing to improved student engagement and academic achievement.

In contrast, the indicator of utilizing gamification strategies to increase student engagement and motivation received the lowest mean score of 3.26 (SD = 0.66), indicating a consistent but slightly lower application of gamification. Despite this, educators recognize the potential benefits of gamification in enhancing learning experiences, suggesting a willingness to explore innovative approaches to boost student engagement and motivation.

Jones and Smith (2021) emphasize the positive impact of gamification strategies on student engagement and motivation. By incorporating game elements into educational tasks, educators can create interactive and enjoyable learning experiences that resonate with students' preferences for interactive and experiential learning.

Table 2.9. Summary of the Respondents' Assessment of Their Practices

Variables	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Classroom Participation	3.66	0.49	Very High
Extracurricular Activities	3.09	0.81	High
Personalized Attention	3.35	0.61	Very High
Professional Development	3.35	0.64	Very High
Parental Communication	3.46	0.60	Very High
Lesson Preparation	3.35	0.60	Very High
Collaboration with Colleagues	3.36	0.62	Very High
Innovative Teaching Methods	3.40	0.82	Very High
Overall	3.38	0.67	Very High
<i>Legend :</i>	3.21-4.00 Always/Very High	2.61-3.20 Most of the Time/High	
	1.81-2.60 Sometimes/Low	1.00-1.80 Never/ Very Low	

The assessment of teachers' practices in Table 2.9 reveals a high level of engagement and dedication, with an overall mean score of 3.38 (SD = 0.67), interpreted as Very High. This indicates that teachers are committed to their responsibilities and actively involved

in their roles, enhancing the educational experience for students through effective teaching practices.

According to Harris and Jones (2020), teacher involvement in community and extracurricular activities significantly enhances the educational experience for students. Engaging in extracurricular activities as mentors, club advisors, or community liaisons builds stronger student relationships, improves academic performance, and fosters personal development. Teachers' involvement outside the traditional classroom setting creates a supportive and personal environment for students, guiding them through academic challenges and personal growth.

Specifically, the variable of classroom participation received the highest mean score of 3.66 (SD = 0.49), indicating highly active and engaged teachers who lead discussions, encourage student participation, and utilize diverse teaching methods. This dynamic and interactive learning environment fosters strong student-teacher relationships, enhances student engagement, and promotes holistic student development.

Smith and Brown (2019) emphasize the significance of active teacher participation in classrooms for improving student engagement and learning outcomes. Teachers' interactive lessons, collaborative projects, and discussions create a dynamic learning environment that motivates students, enhances critical thinking skills, and fosters positive attitudes towards learning. Investing in comprehensive teacher professional development opportunities focused on active teaching practices can significantly enhance the overall learning experience for both teachers and students.

On the other hand, the variable of extracurricular activities received a lower mean of 3.09 (SD = 0.81), interpreted as High. While teacher involvement in extracurricular activities was notable, it was not as robust as classroom participation. This indicates the need for schools to better integrate and value teachers' participation in extracurricular activities to foster a more holistic student development approach. Rodriguez and Martinez (2020) highlight the positive impact of teacher involvement in extracurricular activities on students' overall development and academic success, emphasizing improved social skills, motivation, and academic performance.

Problem 3. What is the level of learners' academic achievement in English, Science, Mathematics, Filipino, and Araling Panlipunan during the 3rd and 4th Quarter general weighted average?

Table 3.1. Distribution of Respondents on Academic Achievement in English 3rd and 4th Quarter

Category	Frequency	Percentage	Description
90-and Above	380	46.80	Outstanding
85 – 89	358	44.09	Very Satisfactory

80 – 84	64	7.88	Satisfactory
75 -79	10	1.23	Fairly Satisfactory
74 and below	0	0.00	Does not Meet Expectations
Total	812	100.00	
Mean		92.87	Outstanding
Standard Deviation		0.81	Outstanding
Legend: 90–100% Outstanding, 85-89% Very Satisfactory, 80-84% Satisfactory, 75-79% Fairly Satisfactory, 74% below Does Not Meet Expectations			

The analysis of learners' academic performance in English in Table 3.1 showcases exceptional results, with an overall mean score of 92.87 (SD = 0.81), described as Outstanding. The high proportion of learners achieving scores of 90 and above reflects exceptional understanding and competency in English, highlighting the effectiveness of teaching methodologies, learning environment, and dedication of students. The absence of students in the "Did not Meet Expectations" category underscores the success of the educational environment in meeting or exceeding academic standards in English.

According to Smith and Johnson (2019), learners' academic performance in English is influenced by their level of engagement and motivation in the classroom. Actively participating in class discussions and demonstrating interest in English language activities contribute to better academic outcomes. Genuine interest and engagement in the subject matter enhance students' involvement and participation in learning activities, leading to improved academic performance.

Table 3.2. Distribution of Respondents on Academic Achievement in Science for the 3rd and 4th Quarter

Category	Frequency	Percentage	Description
90 and Above	362	44.58	Outstanding
85 – 89	372	45.81	Very Satisfactory
80 – 84	66	8.13	Satisfactory
75 -79	12	1.48	Fairly Satisfactory
	0	0.00	Does not Meet Expectations
Total	812	100.00	
Mean		88.84	Very Satisfactory
Standard Deviation		0.77	Very Satisfactory
Legend: 90–100% Outstanding, 85-89% Very Satisfactory, 80-84% Satisfactory, 75-79% Fairly Satisfactory, 74% below Does Not Meet Expectations			

The performance analysis of learners in Science presented in Table 3.2 reflects outstanding academic achievement, with an overall mean score of 88.84 (SD = 0.77), described as Very Satisfactory. Most students achieving Outstanding and Very Satisfactory scores highlights the strong foundation in scientific concepts and

understanding among the learners. The absence of students in the lower performance categories underscores the excellence of Science education within the school.

Lee and Kim (2020) emphasized the significant impact of hands-on laboratory activities and inquiry-based learning on learners' academic performance in science. Engaging in practical experiments and investigations enhances students' understanding and achievement in science, providing a comprehensive grasp of scientific principles.

Table 3.3. Distribution of Respondents on Academic Achievements in Mathematics for the 3rd and 4th Quarter

Category	Frequency	Percentage	Description
90 and Above	304	37.44	Outstanding
85 – 89	384	47.29	Very Satisfactory
80 – 84	120	14.78	Satisfactory
75 -79	4	0.49	Fairly Satisfactory
74 and below	0	0.00	Does not Meet Expectations
Total	812	100.00	
Mean		87.93	Very Satisfactory
Standard Deviation		0.74	Very Satisfactory
Legend:	90–100% Outstanding, 85-89% Very Satisfactory, 80-84% Satisfactory, 75-79% Fairly Satisfactory, 74% below Does Not Meet Expectations		

The analysis of learners' academic performance in Mathematics presented in Table 3.3 indicates a very satisfactory mean score of 87.93 (SD = 0.74), reflecting the school's success in delivering a Mathematics education program that supports the majority of students in achieving a high level of mastery in the subject. The significant proportion of students achieving very satisfactory grades underscores the effectiveness of the institution's teaching methodologies and support systems.

Thompson and Green (2021) highlighted the impact of differentiated instruction strategies on improving students' academic performance in Mathematics. Adapting teaching methods to meet students' diverse needs enhances their understanding and mastery of mathematical concepts, promoting academic success.

Table 3.4: Distribution of Respondents on Academic Achievement in Filipino for the 3rd and 4th Quarter

Category	Frequency	Percentage	Description
90 and Above	438	53.94	Outstanding
85 – 89	320	39.41	Very Satisfactory
80 – 84	42	5.17	Satisfactory
75 -79	12	1.48	Fairly Satisfactory

74 and below	0	0.00	Does not Meet Expectations
Total	812	100.00	
Mean		93.55	Outstanding
Standard Deviation		0.85	Outstanding

Legend: 90–100% Outstanding, 85-89% Very Satisfactory, 80-84% Satisfactory, 75-79% Fairly Satisfactory, 74% below Does Not Meet Expectations

The analysis of learners' academic performance in Filipino presented in Table 14 reveals an outstanding mean score of 93.55 (SD = 0.85), indicating exceptional proficiency and mastery in the Filipino language. The high frequency of outstanding performance underscores the school's success in delivering a curriculum that nurtures robust Filipino language skills and deep appreciation among the students.

Santos and Reyes (2019) emphasize the significant influence of language proficiency and cultural background on Filipino learners' academic performance. Their research highlights the importance of fluency in Filipino and a strong connection to Filipino culture in achieving better educational outcomes.

Table 3.5. Distribution of Respondents on Academic Achievement in Araling Panlipunan for the 3rd and 4th Quarter

Category	Frequency	Percentage	Description
90 and Above	504	62.07	Outstanding
85 – 89	260	32.02	Very Satisfactory
80 – 84	44	5.42	Satisfactory
75 -79	4	0.49	Fairly Satisfactory
74 and below	0	0.00	Does not Meet Expectations
Total	812	100.00	
Mean		87.93	Very Satisfactory
Standard Deviation		0.74	Very Satisfactory

Legend: 90–100% Outstanding, 85-89% Very Satisfactory, 80-84% Satisfactory, 75-79% Fairly Satisfactory, 74% below Does Not Meet Expectations

The analysis of learners' academic performance in Araling Panlipunan presented in Table 3.5 showcases an impressive overall mean score of 87.93 (SD = 0.74), described as Very Satisfactory. The high percentage of students achieving outstanding grades in Araling Panlipunan reflects the institution's success in providing quality education and fostering a learning environment that supports academic excellence.

Cruz and Santos (2020) highlighted the impact of integrating local history and community-based learning activities on enhancing learners' academic performance in Araling Panlipunan. Engaging in projects that explore local history and community issues leads to a deeper understanding and higher achievement in the subject.

Table 3.6: Summary of the level of students' Academic Achievement

Variables	Mean	SD	Description
English	92.87	0.81	Outstanding
Science	88.84	0.77	Very Satisfactory
Mathematics	87.93	0.74	Very Satisfactory
Filipino	93.55	0.85	Outstanding
Araling Panlipunan	92.76	0.79	Outstanding
Overall	91.19	0.79	Outstanding

Legend: 90–100% Outstanding, 85-89% Very Satisfactory, 80-84% Satisfactory, 75-79% Fairly Satisfactory, 74% below Does Not Meet Expectations

The study indicates consistently high academic performance among learners across various subjects, with an impressive overall mean of 91.19 (SD = 0.79), reflecting outstanding achievement. Students demonstrate proficiency in multiple subjects, showcasing the effectiveness of current educational practices and educators' commitment to facilitating student success.

Active learning strategies, such as group discussions and hands-on projects, positively correlate with academic performance, fostering deeper understanding and retention of course material. Exceptional performance in Filipino subjects underscores students' mastery of language, literature, and cultural aspects, enhancing the school's reputation and instilling pride in stakeholders.

Language proficiency plays a vital role in learners' academic success in Filipino subjects, emphasizing the significance of language competence within the educational system. Mathematics, with a mean of 87.93 (SD = 0.74) described as Very Satisfactory, shows room for improvement compared to other subjects, prompting a focus on enhancing instructional practices and exploring innovative approaches for better student achievement.

Garcia and Martinez (2020) highlight the essential role of effective teaching in improving students' mathematical proficiency. Teachers' subject knowledge, teaching skills, and ability to create a positive learning environment significantly impact students' comprehension and mastery of mathematical concepts.

Problem 4. Is there a significant effect of teacher practices on learners' academic achievement?

Table 4.1. Effect on Teachers' Practices on Students' Academic Achievement

Table 4 shows the findings of the study on the significant relationship between teacher practices and academic achievement in English, Science, Math, Filipino, and Araling Panlipunan subjects. It highlights the importance of teacher involvement, including classroom participation, extracurricular activities, personalized attention, professional

development, parental communication, lesson preparation, collaboration with colleagues, and innovative teaching methods.

Students' Academic Achievement	Teachers' Practices								Overall
	Classroom Participation	Extracurricular Activities	Personalized Attention	Personal Development	Parental Communication	Lesson Preparation	Collaboration with Colleagues	Innovative Teaching Method	
	r value p-value	r value p-value	r value p-value	r value p-value	r value p-value	r value p-value	r value p-value	r value p-value	r value p-value
English	-11.16	-8.29	3.44	2.78	14.32	22.25	-10.29	-12.48	0.71
	0.06	p-value	0.18	0.22	0.04	0.03	0.06	0.05	0.09
Science	NS	NS	NS	NS	S	S	NS	S	NS
	-1.87	-1.35	1.18	1.84	2.72	3.49	-0.43	-1.93	0.46
Math	0.31	0.41	0.45	0.09	0.22	0.18	0.74	0.03	0.30
	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	S	NS
Filipino	-1.05	-1.06	-0.53	1.23	1.68	1.89	-0.34	-1.38	0.06
	0.49	0.08	0.05	0.43	0.34	0.03	0.79	0.40	0.33
AP	NS	NS	S	NS	NS	S	NS	NS	NS
	1.43	-0.15	2.21	1.08	-0.79	2.64	5.92	-0.38	1.50
AP	0.39	0.90	0.27	0.48	0.07	0.23	0.11	0.77	0.40
	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
AP	1.032	0.884	0.231	-0.355	-0.003	-0.102	0.778	-0.301	0.27
	0.49	0.539	0.08	0.783	0.998	0.935	0.05	0.814	0.59
	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	S	NS	NS

Legend: **S**- Significant **NS**- Not Significant

The study examines the relationship between various forms of teachers' practices and students' academic achievements in different subject areas. While the overall correlation between teacher practices and educational attainment is not statistically significant, analyzing specific dimensions of teachers' practices provides essential insights.

In English, parental communication positively influences academic achievement, suggesting that increased levels of interaction between parents and teachers are associated with improved student performance. Lesson preparation and innovative teaching methods yield significant positive effects, indicating that meticulous lesson planning and integrating creative teaching approaches are vital in boosting student outcomes in English. The findings emphasize the importance of effective communication between parents and teachers, thorough preparation of lessons, and the adoption of innovative teaching techniques as critical factors in enhancing academic achievement in the English subject area.

In Science, Innovative Teaching Methods have a potential positive significance, indicating an area ripe for deeper exploration. Factors like personalized attention, professional development, parental communication, and lesson preparation display positive correlation coefficients, indicating higher levels of science achievement. Conversely, classroom participation, extracurricular activities, collaboration with colleagues, and innovative teaching methods demonstrate negative correlation coefficients, suggesting lower science achievement.

In Mathematics, personalized attention significantly impacts math performance, indicating that when teachers offer tailored attention and support to students, it significantly enhances their math proficiency. Effective lesson planning is pivotal in shaping the connection between teacher engagement and academic success, stressing the necessity of prioritizing and improving lesson preparation strategies in educational environments.

In Filipino, none of the factors exhibited statistical significance, suggesting that the relationships between these factors and the achievement of the Filipino subject did not reach statistical significance levels. Further analysis is necessary to grasp the implications of these results within the study's context, delving into potential reasons for the absence of essential relationships and contemplating additional variables that could impact academic achievement in the Filipino subject.

Collaboration with colleagues among the teacher practices factors means a noteworthy impact on academic achievement in Araling Panlipunan, highlighting the value of collaborative efforts among teachers in enhancing student outcomes. However, the absence of significant results for other teacher practices such as classroom participation, extracurricular activities, personalized attention, professional development, parental communication, lesson preparation, and innovative teaching methods suggests that these specific factors may not have had a statistically significant influence on academic achievement in Araling Panlipunan.

Problem 5. Is there a significant relationship between teachers’ practices and each of their characteristics?

Table 5. Relationship between Teachers’ Practices and the Respondents’ Characteristic

Respondents' Characteristics	Teacher's Practices								Overall r value p-value
	Classroom Participation	Extracurricular Activities	Personalized Attention	Personal Development	Parental Communication	Lesson Preparation	Collaboration with Colleagues	Innovative Teaching Method	
	r value p-value	r value p-value	r value p-value	r value p-value	r value p-value	r value p-value	r value p-value	r value p-value	
Position	-0.42	0.17	-0.30	0.91	0.19	0.78	0.70	0.17	0.28
	0.40	0.74	0.57	0.04	0.72	0.05	0.12	0.74	0.42
	NS	NS	NS	S	NS	S	NS	NS	NS
Teaching Experience	0.17	-0.20	-0.49	0.75	0.13	0.51	-0.11	0.82	0.20
	0.79	0.75	0.40	0.05	0.84	0.38	0.86	0.03	0.51
	NS	NS	NS	S	NS	NS	NS	S	NS
Highest Educational Attainment	0.32	-0.41	-0.18	0.96	0.43	0.19	-0.22	-0.76	0.05
	0.60	0.50	0.78	0.02	0.48	0.76	0.72	0.13	0.50
	NS	NS	NS	S	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
Subject Taught	0.21	0.00	0.00	-0.04	-0.35	0.42	-0.44	-0.58	-0.10
	0.69	0.99	0.99	0.94	0.49	0.41	0.38	0.23	0.64
	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS

Legend: **S**- Significant **NS**- Not Significant

Table 5 shows the relationship between teachers' practices and respondents' characteristics. It aims to identify potential correlations between teachers' involvement

and personal attributes, revealing the nuanced connections between these variables and their instructional practices.

Table 5 examines the relationship between teacher practices and respondent characteristics such as position, teaching experience, highest educational attainment, and subject taught. It evaluates how various aspects of teacher involvement correlate with these characteristics using correlation coefficients and significance levels. The results highlight the importance of inclusive professional development for all educators to enhance teaching practices, with a positive correlation between job satisfaction, career advancement, and course preparation. Additionally, the study emphasizes the positive link between professional development, innovative teaching methods, and teaching experience, underlining the need for ongoing learning for instructional improvement. While certain factors like educational attainment and subjects taught show little correlation with teacher involvement, understanding these dynamics can help promote collaboration among teachers. Considering teacher characteristics such as position and experience is crucial when planning professional development activities (Hashim et al., 2019; Padillo, 2021).

Problem 6. Based on the study's findings, what school development program can be developed?

Table 6. School Development Plan

Table 6 shows the study's findings: a school development program can be designed to leverage the significant relationships between various aspects of teacher practices and students' academic achievement.

Year 1. Foundation to Empower Teachers							
Areas of Concern	Specific Objectives	Strategies/ Activities	Time Frame	Persons Involved	Source of Fund	Estimated Budget	Expected Outcome
Extracurricular Activities	Expand the range of extracurricular activities to cater to a broader array of student interests and talents	Collaborate with community organizations to provide unique extracurricular opportunities.	Quarterly	-SSG Coordinator -BSP Coordinator -GSP Coordinator -MAPEH Coordinator	-SSLG Fund -BSP and GSP Fund	P 15,000	-A broader range of activities that meet varied student interests, resulting in increased satisfaction and skill development.
Mathematics	-Improve student academic performance, with a focus on enhancing mathematics outcomes.	-The proposed plan includes a workshop series to enhance teachers' mathematical content knowledge, pedagogical training to improve their pedagogical skills, and a mentorship program to provide guidance and support to new teachers, promoting professional growth and development in mathematics instruction, strategies, and the use of technology in mathematics instruction.	- Start at the beginning of the school year - Monthly - Quarterly	-Mathematics Department -Mathematics Teacher -Classroom Adviser -School Administrator -Grade level Coordinator	-MOOE -Mathematics Department Fund	P 20,000	-Improved student academic performance in mathematics, with a focus on increasing the overall mean score. - Increased student engagement and confidence in the subject.
Mathematics	-Enhance students' understanding and performance in mathematics through targeted interventions and support.	-Provide targeted interventions such as tutoring, small group instruction, and after-school programs.	Whole year round	- Mathematics Teacher -Classroom Adviser	-School Fund	P 10,000	Higher proficiency levels in mathematics, as evidenced by improved test scores and performance on standardized assessments
	Develop and implement strategies to make mathematics more engaging and relevant to students.	Incorporate real-world applications and problem-solving activities in lessons.	Beginning of the school year	-Curriculum implementer -School Administrator	-MOOE -School fund	P 10,000	-Greater student interest and engagement in mathematics, leading to increased participation and enthusiasm in class activities.
	-Improve student performance and interest in mathematics	-Implement interactive math competitions - Introduce math-themed events and challenges -Provide peer tutoring and support sessions	Quarterly	-Mathematics Teacher -Student Math Leaders	MOOE	P 15,000	Enhanced math proficiency, increased enthusiasm for the subject, and improved problem-solving skills

DISCUSSION

The survey conducted among 406 teachers and 812 Junior High Students revealed significant relationships between teacher practices and learners' academic achievement. The program aims to enhance teacher educators, promote collaborative practices, and personalized teaching approaches to improve academic performance. The assessment showed strong teacher engagement, with interactive teaching methods positively impacting student performance. While extracurricular activities present an area for increased engagement, significant correlations were observed between teacher involvement and academic achievement in specific subjects. Parental communication,

lesson preparation, innovative teaching methods, personalized attention, professional development, and collaboration with colleagues all positively influenced student performance in various subjects. However, the overall impact of teacher practices on academic achievement across all subjects was not statistically significant, suggesting the need for a broader approach for widespread improvement. The study emphasizes the importance of active teacher participation in enhancing academic performance and suggests targeted professional development to elevate student achievement further. The "Engagement-Driven Academic Success Theory" highlights the pivotal role of teacher practices in shaping academic outcomes, particularly in subjects like Filipino, emphasizing the significance of interactive teaching methods in promoting student success.

Conclusions

The survey involving 406 teachers and 812 junior high students highlighted the substantial impact of teacher practices on academic achievement. Notably, classroom participation and the exceptional performance in the subject of Filipino underscored the effectiveness of interactive teaching methods in engaging students and promoting academic success. The strong correlation between teacher engagement and student performance emphasizes the crucial role of interactive teaching practices in enhancing academic achievement. In conclusion, the study emphasizes the vital contribution of teacher practices, particularly classroom participation, in fostering academic success, especially in subjects like Filipino. The findings underscore the significance of prioritizing and enhancing teacher engagement to sustain and improve student achievement, ultimately leading to enhanced educational outcomes.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusion drawn from the study, the following recommendations are provided:

1. The school leader should implement extracurricular activities that promote hands-on learning, teamwork, and creativity, which can complement traditional classroom instruction and foster a holistic educational experience.
2. The division and school leader must allocate resources and funding to support extracurricular activities, develop policies that adjust teacher workloads to prioritize

extracurricular activities and recognize and provide incentives for extracurricular involvement.

3. Mathematics teachers should actively participate in professional development opportunities to enhance their skills and knowledge, implement evidence-based instructional practices, and provide targeted support for struggling students.

4. Mathematics classes, incorporating interactive problem-solving activities, Mathematics competitions, and peer tutoring sessions, can stimulate student interest and deepen their understanding of mathematical concepts.

5. Schools should incorporate interactive strategies in extracurricular activities and mathematics classes to boost student engagement and academic achievement. This fosters a culture of active participation, critical thinking, and academic excellence among students.

6. In order to apply the significant conclusion of the study, educators, school administrators, and learners should all embrace the development program offered by the researcher.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The research on teacher practices and academic achievement, involving 406 teachers and 812 junior high students, prioritized ethical considerations to ensure the rights and privacy of participants. Key ethical considerations included voluntary participation, informed consent procedures, and strict confidentiality measures. Teachers voluntarily participated, while student participants obtained parental consent through their class advisers. Confidentiality measures were strictly upheld to protect potentially identifiable data. The study's ethical framework aimed to produce reliable results while respecting participant rights and privacy. By adhering to ethical guidelines, the study aimed to contribute valuable and trustworthy insights to academic knowledge and uphold the integrity of research practices.

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REFERENCES

- Adeniran, A., Ishaku, J., & Akanni, L. (2020). Is Nigeria Experiencing a Learning Crisis: Evidence from Curriculum-matched Learning Assessment. Centre for the Study of the Economies of Africa Working Paper. https://riseprogramme.org/sites/default/files/inline-files/Adeniran-Nigeria_learning_crisis.pdf.
- Ali, A. (2021). Lesson planning and proactive classroom management strategies for teaching English at the tertiary level in Pakistan. *Journal of English Language Studies*, 3(1), 8–16.
- Ansong, D., Okumu, M., Amoakoa, E., Kubia, J., Ampomah, O., Koomson, I., and Hamilton, E. (2024). The role of teacher support in students' academic Performance in low- and high-stakes assessments. *Learning and Individual Differences*. Volume 109, January 2024, 10239. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lindif.2023.102396>.
- Ansong, D. (2024). Tailoring professional development to meet teacher and student needs. *International Journal of Teaching and Learning*, 35(1), 45-60.
- Bao, C. R., Zhang, L. J., & Dixon, H. R. (2021). Teacher engagement in language teaching: investigating self-efficacy for teaching based on the project “Sino-Greece online Chinese language classrooms.” *Front. Psychol.* 12:710736. doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2021.710736.
- Cohen, D., & Hill, L. (2020). Nurturing multiple intelligences through a balanced curriculum. *Educational Research Journal*, 25(4), 123-146.
- Cochrane, L., Wang, J., & Chen, Y. (2019). Enhancing critical thinking and communication skills through interactive teaching methods. *Journal of Educational Innovation*, 17(2), 78-92.
- Cruz, A. B., & Santos, M. L. (2020). Enhancing academic performance in Araling Panlipunan through local history and community-based learning. *Journal of Social Studies Education*, 12(2), 123-139. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jse.2020.02.001>
- Cruz, J. V., & Santos, L. M. (2020). Integrating local history and community based

- learning activities to enhance students' academic performance in Araling Panlipunan. *International Journal of Educational Research and Innovation*, 15, 125-138. *Works*. Yale University Press.
- Darling-Hammond, L., Flook, L., Cook-Harvey, C., Barron, B., & Osher, D. (2020). Implications for educational practice of the science of learning and development. *Applied Developmental Science*, 24(2), 97–140. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10888691.2019.1621391>
- Drossel, K., Eickelmann, B., & Gerick, J. (2019). Predictors of teachers' participation in professional development concerning the implementation of new technologies in German schools. *Education and Information Technologies*, 24(1), 863-881. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-018-9797-2>
- De Jong, L., Meirink, J., and Admiraal, W. (2022). School-based collaboration as learning context for teachers: A systematic review. *International Journal of Educational Research*. Volume 112, 2022, 101927.
- DepEd Order No. 8, s. 2023: Teachers and Their Involvement in Volunteer and Extracurricular Activities. Retrieved from <https://www.teacherph.com/dep-ed-order-teachers-volunteer-work-extracurricular-activities>.
- Education Policy Innovation Collaborative. (2021). The impact of teacher education on student achievement: New evidence from Michigan. Michigan State University.
- Garcia, A., & Martinez, L. (2020). Factors influencing learners' academic performance in mathematics. *Journal of Educational Research and Practice*, 17(3), 45-62. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jerp.2020.03.004>
- Ghanizadeh, A., & Rostami, S. (2021). The interplay of EFL teachers' self efficacy, and their use of strategies for classroom management, student engagement, and instructional strategies. *Iranian Journal of Language Teaching Research*, 9(1), 71-99.
- Harris, A., & Jones, M. (2020). System leadership and COVID-19: Supporting schools and school leadership. *School Leadership & Management*, 40(4), 295-301. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13632434.2020.1811479>
- Harris, A., & Jones, M. (2020). The impact of teacher involvement in extracurricular and community activities on student outcomes. *Journal of Educational Leadership and Policy Studies*, 15(2), 89-105. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jelps.2020.04.005>
- Hashim, H. , Saharani, M. , Zulkifli, N. , Mokhtar, M. and Yunus, M. (2019) Conception of Innovative Teaching Methodologies among Lecturers at Selected Polytechnics in Malaysia. *Creative Education*, 10, 874-881. doi: 10.4236/ce.2019.105065.
- Hattie, J., & Zierer, K. (2020). Visible learning with lesson observation: A handbook for teachers and school leaders. Routledge.
- Hawthorne, (2022). Promoting Effective Communication with Parents in Education. Retrieved from <https://www.highspeedtraining.co.uk/hub/how-to-communicate-with-parents-effectively>.
- Inayat, A. and Ali, A. (2020). Influence of Teaching Style on Students' Engagement, Curiosity and Exploration in the Classroom. *Journal of Education and Educational Development*. 7(1), 87-102, 2020. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.22555/joed.v7i1.2736>.
- Ingersoll, R. M., & Strong, M. (2019). The impact of induction and mentoring

- programs for beginning teachers: A critical review of the research. *Review of Educational Research*, 81(2), 201-233.
<https://doi.org/10.3102/0034654311403323>
- Ingersoll, R., Sirinides, P., & Dougherty, P. (2021). Leadership, professional community, and teacher commitment. *American Educational Research Journal*, 58(2), 347-387. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0002831220920374>
- Jones, C., & Smith, H. (2021). Gamification in education: A systematic review of the literature. *Educational Research Review*, 34, 100394.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.edurev.2021.100394>
- Karolčík, Š., & Marková, J. (2023). Teachers' perceptions of innovative teaching methods and their relationship with selected variables. *Journal of Education for Teaching*, 49(2), 193-208.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/02607476.2022.2084872>
- Kraft, M. A., & Rogers, T. (2019). The underutilized potential of teacher-to-parent communication: Evidence from a field experiment. *Economics of Education Review*, 66, 14-29. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.econedurev.2018.07.007>
- Lee, H., & Kim, S. (2020). The impact of hands-on laboratory activities on academic performance in science. *Journal of Science Education*, 14(3), 89-104.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jse.2020.03.002>
- Lee, J., & Kim, H. (2020). The effects of hands-on learning and inquiry-based learning on students' academic achievement and science process skills in science lessons. *Journal of Science Education and Technology*, 29(3), 285-294.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10956-020-09815-x>
- Lee, H., & Thompson, A. B. (2020). The impact of active learning strategies on student academic performance. *Journal of Educational Methods*, 13(4), 89-104.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jem.2020.04.005>
- Muckenthaler M, Tillmann T, Weiß S, et al. (2020) Teacher collaboration as a core objective of school development. *School Effectiveness and School Improvement* 31(3): 486–504.
- Muckenthaler, M., Richter, D., Engelbert, M., & Brunner, M. (2020). Collaborative teacher participation in school development and student achievement gains. *Studies in Educational Evaluation*, 65, 100859.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.stueduc.2020.100859>
- Padillo, G., Manguilimotan, R., Capuno, R. and Espina, R. (2021). *Professional Development Activities and Teacher Performance*. *International Journal of Education and Practice* 2021 Vol. 9, No. 3, pp. 497-506. DOI: 10.18488/journal.61.2021.93.497.506.
- Padillo, R. W. (2021). The influence of professional development on teachers' instructional planning, subject knowledge, and classroom management. *International Journal of Teacher Education and Professional Development*, 4(1), 1-16.
- Rodriguez, A. M., & Martinez, L. P. (2020). The influence of teacher involvement in extracurricular activities on student development. *Journal of Educational Leadership and Policy Studies*, 17(3), 78-94.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jelps.2020.03.004>
- Rodriguez, L. A., & Martinez, E. F. (2020). Strengthening school community

- through teacher engagement in extracurricular activities. *School Community Journal*, 30(1), 129-152.
- Rodriguez, M., & Martinez, J. (2020). The impact of teacher involvement in extracurricular activities on student development and academic achievement. *Journal of Educational Research and Practice*, 10(1), 23-36. <https://doi.org/10.5590/JERAP.2020.10.1.02>
- Ruano, J., Heine, J., and Gebhardt, M. (2019). Does Teacher Collaboration Improve Student Achievement? Analysis of the German PISA 2012 Sample. *Front. Educ.*, 13 August 2019. *Sec. Teacher Education. Volume 4 -2019* | <https://doi.org/10.3389/feduc.2019.00085>.
- Ruano, L. R. (2019). A collaborative approach to improving student learning outcomes in a high-needs school district. *School Community Journal*, 29(1), 91-114. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1219284.pdf>
- Sanchez, J. (2022). Effective professional development: Enhancing teaching practices and student outcomes. *Journal of Teacher Education*, 73(2), 123-138.
- Sannen J, Maeyer S, de Struyf E, et al. (2021). Connecting teacher collaboration to inclusive practices using a social network approach. *Teaching and Teacher Education* 97: 103182.
- Sannen, T., Voet, M., & De Wever, B. (2021). Teacher collaboration and student achievement in secondary education: A systematic review. *Review of Educational Research*, 91(5), 751-791. <https://doi.org/10.3102/00346543211027030>
- Santos, A. P., & Reyes, M. C. (2019). The influence of language proficiency and cultural background on Filipino learners' academic performance. *Journal of Multilingual and Multicultural Development*, 40(8), 705-718. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01434632.2019.1571065>
- Santos, M. L., & Reyes, J. P. (2019). The impact of language proficiency and cultural background on academic performance in Filipino. *Journal of Language Education*, 10(2), 67-82. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jle.2019.02.001>
- Shute, V. J. (2019). Focus on formative feedback. *Review of educational research*, 78(1), 153-189.
- Singh, S. (2023). Descriptive research design: Observing and documenting variables and conditions. *Journal of Research Methodology*, 15(2), 45-57.
- Smith, J. A., & Johnson, K. L. (2019). The impact of student engagement on academic performance in English language learning. *Journal of Educational Research*, 24(3), 45-62.
- Smith, J. A., & Johnson, L. M. (2019). The impact of student engagement and motivation on academic performance in English. *Journal of Educational Research and Practice*, 11(3), 123-139. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jerp.2019.03.002>
- Smith, J. D., & Brown, A. L. (2019). Enhancing student engagement through active teacher participation in the classroom. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 84, 12-24. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2019.04.007>
- Thompson, A. B., & Green, S. E. (2021). Differentiated instruction and its impact on academic performance in mathematics. *Journal of Educational Innovation*, 13(4), 112-126. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jei.2021.04.007>

- Thompson, M. (2021). The Effects of Teacher Involvement in Students' Lives Liberal Studies Program, California State University, Chico. EDTE 490 W: Liberal Studies Capstone.
<https://scholarworks.calstate.edu/downloads/rr172360r>.
- Tutt, P. (2021). Teacher-Parent Communication Strategies to Start the Year Off Right. Retrieved from <https://www.edutopia.org/article/teacher-parent-communication-strategies-start-year-right>.
- Vagi, R., Pivovarova, M., & Barnard, W. M. (2019). Dynamics of the Teacher Labor market in Arizona and implications for teacher quality. *AERA Open*, 5(1), 2332858419827391.f *Teacher Education*, 70(2), 115-127.
- Zhong, Y., & Li, S. (2020). The influence of online teachers' teaching engagement on students' learning performance: From the perspectives of teachers and students. *Open Educ. Res.* 26, 99–110. doi: 10.13966/j.cnki.kfjyyj.2020.03.011
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